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Toxines: De la nature au labo

Toxins: From the wild to the lab

avec le concours de – supported by:

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Proteomics reveals a compartmentalised venom duct in the two phylogenetically related cone snails *Rhombiconus fuscatus* (Born, 1778) and *R. imperialis* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Antonio Caballero FONCUBIERTA^{1,*}, Manuel Jiménez TENORIO², Rafael ZARDOYA³, Juan Carlos Garcia GALINDO¹

¹Universidad de Cádiz, Facultad de Ciencias, Departamento de Química Orgánica-INBIO, Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain.

²Universidad de Cádiz, Facultad de Ciencias, Departamento de CMIM y Química Inorgánica-INBIO, Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain. ³Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN-CSIC), Madrid, Spain.

*Corresponding author, e-mail: antonio.caballero foncubierta@alum.uca.es

Rhombiconus fuscatus (Born, 1778) and *R. imperialis* (Linnaeus, 1758) are two phylogenetically related cone snails present in the Indo-Pacific region that feed on polychaetes belonging to the family Amphinomidae (Lamarck, 1818) known as fireworms. Their venom duct, where conotoxins are contained in, is noticeably divided into two sections distinguished by their colour (red in the distal part from the bulb and pale yellow in the proximal region). The proteomic study of the two regions of both species was carried out using two mass spectrometric techniques: ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS) and liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). 19 conotoxins, previously described in *R. imperialis* at a transcriptomic level, were identified using UHPLC-MS while LC-MS/MS analysis was able to identify 74 generic proteins and 65 conotoxins present in the venom duct of *R. imperialis* and/or *R. fuscatus*. The combined use of both spectrometric techniques permitted to identify 28 conotoxins from the transcriptome of *R. imperialis* in any of both species. Also, the number and intensity of the conotoxins identified by UHPLC-MS allowed us to study the differences in the venom composition according to three variables: region of the venom duct (proximal or distal), species (*R. fuscatus* or *R. imperialis*) and intraspecific variability. UHPLC-MS analysis showed a higher amount of conotoxins in the proximal part of the venom duct while the distal section was found to be mostly composed of low molecular weight non-peptide molecules suggesting an ecological significance: the proximal part contains most of the defense-evoked conotoxins while the small molecules of the distal region would be used for prey capture. Principal component analysis on the conotoxins' intensity showed differences in the peptide composition of *R. fuscatus* and *R. imperialis* supporting the hypothesis that both are differentiated species although this hypothesis should be confirmed by genomic studies. It was found little intraspecific variability among the three individuals of *R. imperialis* and between the two individuals of *R. fuscatus*, which supports the hypothesis that dietary breadth is positively correlated with venom complexity in cone snails. The 28 identified conotoxins were modeled using AlphaFold2 in order to obtain their hypothetical 3D structures, which were compared against a database of other conotoxins' tertiary structures using RUPÉE. This *in silico* study allowed us to propose a potential molecular target for four conotoxins.

Keywords: cone snail, conotoxin, proteomics, *Rhombiconus fuscatus*, *Rhombiconus imperialis*.

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